

**educ
arts!**

EDUCATOR'S GUIDE

Human Rights education through
Arts, Culture and Creativity

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Let's get started: EducArts! Project

Education explains the past, justifies the present and predicts the future, so educating in values and rights is a necessity rather than an end in itself. It is one of the many jobs of teachers, professors and educators to transmit citizenship and democratic values to shape the societies of the future, however, many of them find themselves without the tools to facilitate this knowledge and skills in a meaningful way, and sometimes the used methods do not achieve the expected results.

After detecting this pedagogical need, the EducArts! team decided to act through the development of this guide, which has as its backbone the use of active, participatory methodologies and art and creativity for the personalization of learning and the assimilation of knowledge by students, who, at least in the pilot experiences, were involved with the project as they did not feel alien to its contents, acquiring a community and even global vision of the fundamental rights that protect and respect lives regardless of the borders that separate them.

Structure and purpose

Structure and purpose

The teaching of human rights is key to developing a citizenry that is aware of human rights violations. Instilling respect, peace and **cooperation among people** is an objective that educators should permanently focus on, as this human ability is key to achieving a better future.

Creative and artistic strategies in the classroom provide positive educational benefits that have yet to be exploited: Some researchers point to significant improvements in terms of classroom cooperation, expression of one's own feelings and emotions, or acceptance and enthusiasm for the content.

Active, participatory and democratic educational practices deeply improve knowledge acquisition while enhancing the positive interdependence between learners, instilling values of respect, cooperation and interaction; and training significant competences such as negotiation, social skills and mutual support.

This handbook for facilitators is a resource to be used by professionals involved in non-formal education from two perspectives: on the one hand, to discover or deepen how art, culture and creativity are useful tools at the service of promoting human rights and European Union values, and on the other hand, it is designed for professionals who train and educate in citizenship and social justice, to help them find new practical, participatory and creative ways to channel their teachings. It is an opportunity to introduce new creative approaches in a practical way in educational tools or design training experiences. The materials developed will serve to inspire new approaches or replicate tested proposals. It is useful to help prepare and run non-formal education sessions through artistic or creative, participatory and people-centred workshops.

Complementary to this manual, there is an existing logbook for educators or learners, with creative and artistic activities and exercises to reflect on human rights, which can be used by individuals or groups, with or without a teacher.

Project rational: context and goals

The EducArts! methodology improves democratic education through the use of narratives based on art and creativity as an attractive medium to spread values beyond borders. In reality, young people, those on whom the future of the European Union will rest, are the ones who most need innovative and motivating methods to strengthen their civic engagement.

In this way, the general objective of the EducArts! is to foster citizens' understanding of their fundamental rights, Europe's common values and their common cultural wealth, thus fostering democratic participation across the Union in the unpredictable post-COVID context.

Civic engagement in the times of crisis: The recent COVID-19 pandemic has aroused public concern about the drastic measures that the different States have taken in the face of the Health Emergency and that have led to the limitation of some Civil Rights. Thus, debates have arisen on how to manage the restriction of rights when dealing with emergency situations, and how to strengthen the Welfare State in times of difficulty to safeguard the economic and social rights of the population. In the same way, the serious situation highlighted the need to guarantee universal and popular access to art and culture, elements with educational, emotional and healthy and positive recreational functions. The time has come to challenge radicalism and Euroscepticism with new social and intercultural perspectives that help safeguard the future of the European Union. For this reason, it is a critical time to show and learn how common European values are the best way to overcome adversity together. On the other hand, it is the young people who will lead this future, who must feel European politics and values as their own.

Specific objectives

1. Improve the skills of educators

Involved in the field of lifelong learning, using audiovisual narratives and creative-artistic methods as a means to reinforce student motivation and the transmission of positive values.

2. Contribute to values education

Especially groups at risk of social exclusion, through the use of innovative and participatory teaching methods based on co-creation and participatory creativity.

3. Promote creative laboratories

In local community spaces to promote citizen participation, social inclusion and lifelong learning through the promotion of culture and the arts.

4. Offer learning opportunities

Through the development of creative, artistic and cultural skills

5. Spread the Erasmus spirit

Among all citizens and generations, and especially among young people and creatives, as a way of exchanging experiences with which to express their European identity and the feeling of belonging in terms of common values, helping to build and strengthen ties of solidarity between the European communities.

Target Audiences

Institutions

Their involvement in educational change is key to the success of the European and Democratic values among citizens from all around the world. Their job is to organize and promote the innovative methods supporting the new world educators and students, allowing them to drive the change revolutionising the educational scene.

Students

Understanding them as anyone who wishes to participate in training processes around the promotion of democratic values and human rights with an artistic/cultural approach. EducArts! focuses mainly on young people between the ages of 15 and 29, since they are the ones who will lead the democratic future and, therefore, they must feel European politics and values as their own, will underpin the future of the European Union and innovative and inspiring methods are needed to engage them.

Educators

Seeking to address the co-creation of educational methods that allow adult educators to use narrative techniques as a motivational and participatory element for students that, in a flexible and adaptive way, allow the use of audiovisual content, artistic creations, debates, exhibitions, or other cultural elements that make it possible to identify, address or promote issues related to human rights and the values that define European communities.

Some keywords

Before starting this journey, everyone reading this manual should familiarize themselves with some terms that will normally appear in the following paragraphs, they are specific and related to the educational and creative field. One of the main bases of this manual is being useful for everyone, not just teachers and professionals, but the reading of these definitions will be useful for them too as a way of activating previous knowledge.

Active methodologies: Compound of educational strategies that, in contrast with the traditional ones, empower the students while improving knowledge retention and understanding, attention towards learning and skills and competences acquisition (Konopka, C. L., Adaime, M. B., & Mosele, P. H., 2015; Moya, E. C., 2017).

The student at the center of learning: Students should be active agents on their own learning, taking responsibility on learning and engaging the class and their partners in the process.

Facilitator: On active methodologies, the teacher assumes the role of facilitator of the educational process. Organizing, structuring, guiding and helping the true protagonists of learning: The students (Kelly, C., 2016).

Inclusiveness: Practices, attitudes and values of respect, democracy, equity, diversity, justice, cooperation and participation towards others, regardless of their personal characteristics such as socioeconomic status, gender, ethnicity, religion, educational needs... (Moran, A., 2007).

Cooperative learning: Based on dividing the class on small heterogeneous groups promoting co-learning by cooperation to reach the set goals on scheduled tasks, in contrast with individualistic and competitive learning (Erbil, D. G., 2020).

Heterogeneous groups: Multi-level and inclusive groups which foster cooperation and respect amongst others, aiming at high achievements for everyone.

Project-based learning: Technique that recognizes experience as the powerful educational tool that it is, setting goals for students to reach while letting them experiment and research in the process (Kokotsaki, D., Menzies, V., & Wiggins, A., 2016; Krajcik, J. S., & Blumenfeld, P. C., 2006).

Service learning: Based on citizen learning, tries to provide educational experiences to students while involving them in their own context, creating networks of mutual support and fostering democratic and cooperative values and civic responsibility (Felten, P., & Clayton, P. H., 2011; Sandoval, L. A., 2017).

Comprehensive development: Final goal of education - Emotional, social, creative, intellectual, professional and individual development.

Arts as a tool to educate in Rights

Arts as a tool to educate in Rights

One main aim of education is the comprehensive development of the individual. Therefore, it is not only necessary to focus on the content of the different subjects, but also to emphasize other fundamental aspects. Rights education encapsulates three key areas for human being's development: education for social justice, education for citizenship and education in values:

Social justice education calls for multiculturalism, respect, equity, participation, cooperation and democracy for all learners as a way of achieving a more fair and equal future, inclusive for all (Hyttén, K., & Bettez, S. C., 2011).

Global Citizenship Education refers to all those actions aimed at preparing a person for incorporation into the global society on a professional, social and individual level. The ultimate aim is the meaningful and positive participation in society for the development of individuals and the community itself, ensuring peaceful coexistence and acquiring in the process awareness of belonging to the community and what this implies (Ekanayake, K., Shukri, M., Khatibi, A., & Azam, S. M., 2020).

Values education tries to respond to the need to transmit attitudes and feelings that are socially acceptable and beneficial to the community among students. In this way, they assimilate them as their own through a process of internalization, favoring their personal and social development (Ercilla, M. A., & Tejada, N. B., 1999).

These three dimensions that make up human rights education should be taken into account and addressed individually and as a group. Through the use of creative and artistic tools, the learning of content can be promoted in a meaningful and experiential way. This enhances rights education in three ways: it innovates the learning process itself, making it more interesting and engaging for the population; it improves the retention and internalization of knowledge, which is consistent with the objectives; and it provides usable and useful physical resources, making it possible to expand knowledge by exposing learning outcomes to the community.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights

On October 24, 1945, in the aftermath of World War II, the United Nations was born as an intergovernmental organization with the purpose of saving future generations from the devastation of war and other international conflicts.

The Statutes of the United Nations established six main organs, including the General Assembly, the Security Council, the International Court of Justice, and in relation to human rights, an Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC).

The statutes of the United Nations gave the Economic and Social Council the power to establish “commissions in economic and social fields for the promotion of human rights...”. One of these was the United Nations Commission on Human Rights, which, under the chairmanship of Eleanor Roosevelt, was charged with the creation of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The Declaration was drafted by representatives from all regions of the world and encompasses all legal traditions. Formally adopted by the United Nations on December 10, 1948, it was the most universal human rights document in existence, outlining the thirty fundamental rights that form the basis for a democratic society.

Representatives of the United Nations from all regions of the world formally adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights on December 10, 1948.

Eleanor Roosevelt with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights

Following this historic act, the Assembly called on all member countries to publish the text of the Declaration and “that it be distributed, displayed, read and displayed mainly in schools and other educational institutions, regardless of the political status of the countries or territories.”.

Today, the Declaration is a continuously evolving document that has been accepted as a contract between a government and its people throughout the world. According to the Guinness Book of World Records, it is the most translated document in the world.

In the annexes we reproduce the text of the official document of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which can be found at the end of this manual.

European Union values

The European Union (EU) is a union of States that decide to join together to achieve common political objectives and that they do so, not only because they understand that this is the best way to achieve their own interests, but also because they understand that their political systems and social are based on a series of fundamental principles and values that are common to all member states. The EU, then, is not only a union of interests, but it is mainly a union of values, given that, if these common values did not exist, the mere union of interests would not be sustained and would crack at the first conflict or divergence that arise between the Member States. The EU's values are laid out in article 2 of the Lisbon Treaty and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and are listed below:

1. **Human dignity:** Human dignity is inviolable. It must be respected, protected and constitutes the real basis of fundamental rights.
2. **Freedom:** Freedom of movement gives citizens the right to move and reside freely within the Union. Individual freedoms such as respect for private life, freedom of thought, religion, assembly, expression and information are protected by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.
3. **Democracy:** The functioning of the EU is founded on representative democracy. A European citizen automatically enjoys political rights. Every adult EU citizen has the right to stand as a candidate and to vote in elections to the European Parliament. EU citizens have the right to stand as a candidate and to vote in their country of residence, or in their country of origin.
4. **Equality:** Equality is about equal rights for all citizens before the law. The principle of equality between women and men underpins all European policies and is the basis for European integration. It applies in all areas. The principle of equal pay for equal work became part of the Treaty of Rome in 1957.
5. **Rule of law:** The EU is based on the rule of law. Everything the EU does is founded on treaties, voluntarily and democratically agreed by its EU countries. Law and justice are upheld by an independent judiciary. The EU countries gave final jurisdiction to the European Court of Justice - its judgments have to be respected by all.
6. **Human rights:** Human rights are protected by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. These cover the right to be free from discrimination on the basis of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation, the right to the protection of your personal data, and the right to get access to justice.

Why use Art to educate in Rights?

The fight against radicalism and Euroscepticism requires new social and intercultural perspectives can help safeguard the future of the EU. Debates are emerging on how to manage the restriction of rights to deal with emergency situations such as health pandemics, armed conflicts, energy restrictions or economic crises, and how to sustain the Welfare State in times of difficulty to safeguard the economic and social rights of the population.

Thus, the current moment is critical to learn how common European values help to overcome adversity together. Especially young people who will lead this future, who must feel European politics and values as their own, as global challenges demand cross-country collaboration.

The proposal of EducArts! methodology consists of improving democratic education through the use of narratives based on Arts and creativity as an attractive means to spread these values beyond borders.

It is young people, those on whom the future of the EU will be based, who most need innovative and motivating methods to engage them. In this way, the main objective of this training methodology is to promote citizens' understanding of their fundamental rights, the common values of Europe and our common cultural wealth, thus promoting democratic participation throughout the Union in the current unpredictable context.

Acquired skills

Considering educators as a broad-spectrum group, from teachers in adult education centers to support tutors for people at risk of exclusion from NGOs, EducArts! works on the lack of competencies and skills to connect with the citizens who are the object of education in values. Educators, in addition to offer didactic competences, must meet key skills necessary in today's world (such as audio-visual and digital), in addition to certain creative skills that allow to motivate the youngest. Specifically, EducArts! addresses competences in narratives so that testimonies, ideas and values are shared by the citizens themselves through storytelling.

Educational practices

Educational practices

Active methodologies, as opposed to traditional methodologies, are those that seek, above all, to place the student at the center of learning. In this way, the teacher assumes the role of facilitator of learning. Years ago, the teacher was an authority figure whose duty was to provide knowledge to the students. With active methodologies, students become active subjects in the educational process, having more than ever the responsibility of their own learning, guided and supervised by the teacher (Konopka, C. L., Adaime, M. B., & Mosele, P. H., 2015).

There are various techniques derived from active methodologies, one of them being cooperative learning, which produces a substantial improvement in learning by really connecting with the students. In the classic structure of the cooperative class, there are several phases. In the first phase, students' prior knowledge of the subject to be learnt is activated, which can be done with videos, open questions, photographs... In this way, the teacher manages to capture the attention of the audience, which will make them feel involved in the second phase of content presentation. The third phase is based on cooperative work among the members of a group, which ideally would be heterogeneous in terms of its members. In the fourth and final phase, participants engage in a general group discussion in which they reach firm conclusions. Students' efforts are appreciated and reinforced (Ilyas, M., Ma'rufi, F., & Syamsuddin, A., 2020). The facilitator's duty in the process is to guide the learners through the process ensuring positive outcomes and the smooth functioning of the learning group. The facilitation process must also ensure educational inclusiveness, taking care of key aspects such as equal distribution of protagonism, minimizing the effects of existing power relations in the classroom or maximizing educational inclusion (Kelly, C., 2016; Moran, A., 2007).

Project-based learning is also one of the many active methodologies. It seeks to involve students through the interconnection of educational axes, based on a specific topic. In the process, the student learns to investigate, to collaborate, to structure knowledge, to solve problems and to develop in a creative and dynamic environment (Kokotsaki, D., Menzies, V., & Wiggins, A., 2016; Krajcik, J. S., & Blumenfeld, P. C., 2006). The proposal is based on the personalisation of learning: students are involved, as they are active subjects, and construct knowledge in a meaningful way.

Service learning, on the other hand, is based on involving students in the community in which they are located, in order to create a positive two-way relationship between them and society. By doing so, the individual learns and the community is benefited. In the process, channels of communication and cooperation between stakeholders are established and the learner acquires social responsibility, social skills and a sense of community, which promotes his or her personal development (Felten, P., & Clayton, P. H., 2011; Sandoval, L. A., 2017). This concept is closely related to the notion of the educating city. In them, education is conceived as a process that happens in any place or environment, which should be addressed by the administration and governments. In this way, community consciousness

EducArts! Methodology

EducArts! Methodology

EducArts! bases its methodological proposal on three fundamental pillars, that consist of basic perspectives and guiding questions which any educator must take into account in order to structure artistic and creative activities within the framework of human rights education. These three perspectives have associated social problems, with the consequent intervention proposals addressed by the EducArts! team. They should be explained to the student in every single activity related to the EducArts! Project.

Taking into account these three perspectives, 7 different ArtScenarios have been designed, which are suggestions of typologies of activities. These must be defined by the educators, adapting them to the possibilities of each specific center and taking into account the available materials and the needs or potentials of the students for whom they are designed.

In this way, the educator knows the philosophy behind the activities and the key points to take into account (EducArts! Perspectives), starts from concrete and structured proposals with pre-set objectives and suggested artistic actions and applications (ArtScenarios) to create adapted educational spaces that are coherent with the environment and the students (Learning Situations).

EducArts! Visions and Perspectives

The EducArts! methodology combines three different visions through which it is intended to introduce the learner, in a natural way, to human rights and European values. These visions should be explained to the students at the beginning of each activity, for them to understand what the session is going to be about by activating previous knowledge or creating a general basis.

Looking at Human Values

The first look that addresses EducArts! methodology is the vision on Human Rights. This vision is based on universal values, principles and rules, typical of human dignity. Thus, aspects related to freedom, life, equality, security or social welfare, among others, are addressed.

Looking at Art, Culture and Creativity

The other look of EducArts! is, of course, the creative and cultural perspective that, using elements such as the arts, make it possible to create a closer link between great ideas and values, and the human being in his daily life, desires and emotions.

Looking at Human Being

Finally, this learning methodology looks at the human being, in the sense that both values and rights as well as creative expression must attend to the concerns and understanding of the other, so that the education achieved attends to a common good, beyond personal growth of the learner, who can become an authentic actor of social change. To do this, an Human-Centered Design is used to build the ArtScenarios, as explained below.

What we don't know cannot be part of us

Our actions are driven by rights and values. If we as society are able to find unanimity on issues such as the right to life, cultural diversity... in short, regarding everything that gives us human dignity can be legally secured.

However, international mechanisms, laws and regulations propose a utopian scenario to address and a reactive approach when they are violated. Everyone has in mind the international condemnations of the serious crimes of Humanity. This context generates a vague ideal, a set of abstract ideas.

1 HUMANS
VALUES

It is common for people to ask what human rights are or what are the values of the EU and not be able to find a concise answer since "what we do not know cannot be part of us".

The educator must transmit to the students that it is normal not to know them, not knowing how to define them and make them understand that the objective of the ArtScenario is not to study human rights and values, but to try to internalize them, to make them part of themselves. At the end of the activity, you can return to them to find out what they have learned.

As an example, to introduce the student in the context of human rights and EU values, the following activities are proposed:

- Make a brainstorm of words that will be placed with post-its on a panel to reinforce the strongest ones. To carry out this activity it is not necessary to have previous knowledge, it is about being spontaneous and letting the words flow naturally.
- If the target audience demands a more intellectual approach to Human Rights and the common values of the EU, explanatory videos can be viewed. Those can be found on the annex 2

What we don't use disappears, it doesn't exist

One of the biggest challenges in different pedagogical settings, is to bring life to abstract concepts. In order to do so, one central approach is to try to create different subjective meanings for example by try to connect these concepts to the everyday life of the learners or by make these concepts more concrete by other means. In our context, these goal means to show participants that Human Rights and European Values are not utopian concepts, but create concrete meanings and improvements for their everyday life instead.

To explain this part, educators can start by launching a series of questions such as: How and who exercises human rights? Where do we find them? Do we know how to put them into practice? Do we know examples?

2 ART, CULTURE & CREATIVITY

A practical way to apply this approach is learning from others, copying strategies, hacking ways of seeing things, using nearby examples that help the student understand and internalize these values from everyday life.

Thus, following this perspective means to make a participatory approach, involving the students so that they find real situations in which the deployment of the Declaration of Human Rights or the values of the European Union can be identified. and make a difference. One other way to make human rights and European values concrete

is to think of ways to advance these values for future societies and global challenges. In this and many other contexts, creativity and the ability of adapt existing ideas of coworking A video about it can be found on Annex 2.

Certainly, it can be difficult to take action on Human Rights since many questions arise in this process:

- What are the key or most important human rights?
- Who is in charge of identifying them? Who enforces them and how?

Arts, culture and creativity are an inexhaustible source of resources in which to seek the reflection of rights and values through the eyes of others. Throughout history, multiple examples can be found in which Art and Culture are used as an engine of social transformation, since artists through their creations transmit not only emotions, but also messages and make the public reflect on their existence, social problems or life in general.

On Annex 2 there are some links that can be used to explain how different artistic expressions are used to highlight the rights and values of society.

What grows, grows from within: From people to action

To find suitable ways to action it is proposed to use the concept of "Human Centered Design" Design.

The Human Centered Design can be described as a process that starts from an approach based on empathy with the people for whom is the activities are being designed and has

as its goal the provision of innovative solutions that fit those people and their subjective needs. An explanation of this concept can be found in the Annex 2.

3 HUMAN-CENTERED
APPROACH

In the case of the EducArts! methodology, Human Centered Design is not applied to find solutions, but to design creative or artistic scenarios that facilitate learning about European values and human rights. The objective is the cultural experience itself, it is the experience of values, the "ArtScenario".

With these premises, the seven learning situations have been developed among which the educator can choose which part of the people he wants to work on to create her or his ArtScenario.

ArtScenarios

EducArts! has identified 7 possible types of ArtScenarios in the research carried out, although this is not intended to be exhaustive. In this methodology, an ArtScenario consists of a proposal which will imply the deployment by the learners of actions associated with key and specific competences, which contribute to learning development. This situation will include elements to consider, such as educator, learner, and subject matter, as well as teaching materials, equipment, and/or physical facilities. This is what EducArts! call ArtScenarios.

ArtScenarios involve various fields of action: observe, share, analyze, express, transform, design, and transcend. This allows the educator to work in a learning situation through a multitude of activities that relate rights and values to arts and creativity. It is the educator's choice how many learning situations to address (one or several) according to the educational objectives. In any case, each action must consider the three visions (values, creative and human-centered) to achieve results. Regardless of the selected learning situation, when working with the EducArts! methodology, the educator must put the students in the situation, for this it is recommended to make an introduction that consists of three steps, directly related to the EducArts! perspectives below described. Complementary to this manual, there is a toolkit for educators available where they can find resources and examples regarding ArtScenarios. The designed ArtScenarios are the following:

1

Through artist's eye
Your material context

Context: Reflections with arts and creative practitioners, Art and culture for human rights.
Actions: Observe, explore.
Learning situations, possible applications: Intervention with objects, performance.

Approaches

<p><i>Creative</i> Give new meaning to objects. Understanding the artist's gaze. Talk from a creative perspective</p>	<p><i>Human rights</i> Discovering the rights we have and do not see.</p>	<p><i>People in the center</i> Looking at our environment, at the objects around us.</p>
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Skills: Raising awareness, Critical and Abstract thinking, Strategic vision, visual literacy.
Competencies: Debate managing, solving through enquire, bottom-up approaches.
Definition: By using interviews both professionals and stakeholders from different conditions and fields reflect on how their performance within the Cultural and Creative Industries adds value to the promotion or denunciation of human rights.

<p>2</p> <p>Meeting value From your community, your people</p>	<p>Context: Listening to communities from the perspective of social value. Actions: Sharing, social mediation. Learning situations, possible applications: Photovoice, Street art with avatars of people.</p>
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Approaches

<p><i>Creative</i> Community art, collective action.</p>	<p><i>Human rights</i> The rights of others, different and equal.</p>	<p><i>People in the center</i> Look at our community, at the people around us, with whom we share spaces and experiences.</p>
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Skills: Debate managing, Public speaking, Listening-understanding others.
Definition: Activity based on discovering our community or those around us, being able to put ourselves in others' shoes, thus immersing ourselves in their life and culture in order to understand them. Also, to reflect on the similarities and differences in order to raise awareness of the existing inequalities in rights.

<p>3</p> <p>Digital is a place Your screen, the interfaces</p>	<p>Context: Participatory and digital design to solve local needs. Actions: Analyze, Digital Narratives. Learning situations, possible applications: Diseño, Intervención en redes sociales, Videojuegos, Fotografía, Cine</p>
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Approaches

<p><i>Creative</i> Visual narratives, cinema. Digital dystopias.</p>	<p><i>Human rights</i> The distortion of rights.</p>	<p><i>People in the center</i> Get to know the interfaces we wear, the worlds we walk through.</p>
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Skills: Critical culture, Artistic production, Emotional expression, Story-telling
Definition: Activity exploring the impact of screens and technological media in creative applications as a form of expression in everyday life and their use for or against human rights.

4	<p>Talk ideas Your words</p>	<p>Context: Public podium: elevating the social role of civil society. Driving Change. Actions: Expressing, public speaking. Learning situations, possible applications:</p>
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Approaches

<p><i>Creative</i> Theatre, characters, storytelling.</p>	<p><i>Human rights</i> Visibilising needs, democratic values and freedom of expression.</p>	<p><i>People in the center</i> Convey ideas, experiences, concerns. To elevate speeches.</p>
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Skills: Body language and expression, Story-telling.
Definition: Use of the performing arts to involve students in activities for the expression of rights or the protesting of injustices in order to achieve group reflections in which conclusions are reached through corporality.

5	<p>Melt your fears Your insights</p>	<p>Context: Active listening to society, processing the "discourses of anger" through the actions of artists. Angerbox. Actions: Transform, mediation. Learning situations, possible applications: Dance.</p>
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Approaches

<p><i>Creative</i> Reverse energy, activate intuition, the subconscious, improvisation.</p>	<p><i>Human rights</i> Lack of understanding of the rights of others, empathy for the rights of others, empathy for the rights of others.</p>	<p><i>People in the center</i> Your screen, the interfaces. Get to know the interfaces we wear, the worlds we walk through.</p>
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Skills: Expressing emotions, creating and building through destruction, transformation.
Definition: In this activity, negative attitudes, symbols or ideas are transformed into positive ones through the use of various creative techniques. Negative and harmful personal and external questions are addressed for further transformation.

6
Utopia and dystopia
 Your future

Context: Designing co-created future scenarios to narrate ideas and fears about the future. The future is a dilemma.
Actions: Design, co-creation, creativity.
Learning situations, possible applications: Utopian architecture, design your spaces.

Approaches

<i>Creative</i> Designing utopias, scenarios, dreams.	<i>Human rights</i> The preservation of rights, the evolution of these rights.	<i>People in the center</i> Imagine our ideal future.
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Skills: Imagination, expression of desires.
Definition: Activity in which students are led to imagine possible future societies with the aim of modifying the negative aspects of the present and incorporating the positive ones, trying to bring students closer to the ideal of society, with the goal of pursuing it.

7
Sharing to integrate
 What you see

Context: Making a case for whistleblowing by asking questions, moral courage.
Actions: Transcending, empathizing, vision of the other.
Learning situations, possible applications: Photovoice, Building a story.

Approaches

<i>Creative</i> The images we receive, art as social protest.	<i>Human rights</i> Passivity in the face of rights violations.	<i>People in the center</i> To look beyond what each of us is. To look at others, to understand the images of denunciation.
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Skills: Social denunciation, alternative view, empathy,
Definition: Social denunciation of the passivity or ignorance in various strata of society in the face of inequalities or human rights violations. Exploration of the external, beyond one's own, for the mobilization of active and committed attitudes.

Learning situations

EducArts! considers essential the implementation of pedagogical proposals that, based on the interest of citizens, allow them to build knowledge with autonomy and creativity from their own learning and experiences. Learning situations represent an effective tool to integrate knowledge through meaningful and relevant tasks and activities to solve problems creatively and cooperatively, reinforcing self-esteem, autonomy, reflection and responsibility.

For effective skills acquisition, learning situations must be well contextualized and respectful of the learner's experiences and their different ways of understanding reality, and they should be made up of tasks of increasing complexity, whose resolution entails the construction of new learning. Thus, it seeks to offer the learner the opportunity to connect their learning and apply it in contexts close to their daily lives, favoring their commitment to their own learning. Learning situations constitute a component that, aligned with the principles of Design for All, allows learning to learn and lays the foundations for lifelong learning by promoting flexible and accessible pedagogical processes that adjust to the needs, characteristics, and different learning rhythms of the learner.

The situations must start from the approach of clear and precise objectives, but they must also propose scenarios that favor different types of grouping, from individual work to group

work, allowing students to progressively assume personal responsibilities and act cooperatively in the creative resolution of the challenge posed.

The implementation must involve oral production and interaction, and also include the use of resources in different supports and formats, both analogue and digital. Learning situations must promote aspects related to common interest, sustainability, and/or democratic coexistence, essential for learners to prepare themselves to respond effectively to the challenges of the 21st century.

A learning situation has the following characteristics:

In this way, using this way of teaching, the educator must develop a structured proposal, aimed at solving a previously raised problem. Thus, a situation on which to work must be identified in order to design a coherent training action. Of course, the problem must be related to values or rights, while the products to be developed will be based on creative productions. The steps to follow for the design of a learning situation are:

- Identification of the interests of the participants
- Combine them with the pedagogical interest of the educator
- Specify objectives, skills to work on, and evaluation (if any)
- Definition of action to be carried out: challenge, problem, product, ...
- Decide activities and resources to use.

Pilot experiences and results

Pilot experiences and results

The different pilot experiences took place in three main geographical locations: Madrid (Spain), Vienna (Austria) and Faro (Portugal), the headquarters of the three sister organizations promoting the project. They aimed to collaborate with other entities such as universities, cultural centers or institutes in order to give volunteer students the possibility to learn about human rights from creative and artistic perspectives. The continuous feedback from students and professionals associated with the project was key to the continuous improvement of the project thanks to the constant communication between the entities. The characteristics of the people participating are varied in terms of gender, sexual orientation, age, aspirations or socio-cultural groups, but the results, positive in all cases, lead us to believe that proposals such as EducArts! make sense.

On the pages below there is a summary of the pilot experiences carried out, with their characteristics and general guidelines followed by the educational groups. These pilot experiences are based on the 7 ArtScenarios conducted during the EducArts! Project. The different learning situations have been adapted to the characteristics of each individual context and group of students. The learning outcomes of the different scenarios are also included, to give others a better idea of what the learners worked on. The EducArts! team encourage everyone who reads this handbook to replicate the activities in their educational centers.

Building Co-Learning ArtScenarios to Promote Human Values

Andrei Serotini, Vivaldo Luís, Dovilė Imbrasaitė, Soraia Luz, Ana Sofia Martins, Ana Monteiro

Location

Tomás Cabreira Secondary School (Faro, Portugal). Art, Design and Communication classroom.

Students

19 students with ages between 17 and 24

Materials

Chalkboard
Projector
Computers

Artistic Component

Graphic design

Goal

Promote respectful listening, communication, negotiation, cooperation and debate to generate an accurate, comprehensive and shared description of human rights.

Procedure

The session started introducing the project of EducArts!. Following task was to find out how many people are aware about human rights. So the session facilitator wrote "Human rights" on the blackboard and started asking the students separately what word comes to their minds when they think about human rights. Most of the students were pretty active and aware. After that, a video about human rights was shown. This short video was seeking to show the students that people are not so much aware about it, which led to the "What we don't understand cannot be part of us" methodology. And then the facilitator briefly explained the history of Human Rights. The following step was to present the full methodology of EducArts!

To get students' views on human rights, we asked them to respond to several statements by answering how much they agree or disagree with it (Annex 3).

The board was split in half, with one side saying "Agree" and the other "Disagree". It helped them to understand what other colleagues think and to accept different opinions. After explaining the whole methodology, the class moved on to the timing of activities. First of all, a group of 19 people was divided into 6 different groups, 3 of which worked with Poster and the other 3 worked with Art that would promote values and human rights. The groups discussed their ideas and started working on the tasks.

The educators organized a discussion with the students, during which the different groups presented their work, which we printed out before coming to the school.

Learning Outcomes

Utopias and dystopias

Concha Maza, Elena Martín, Antonio Serrano, Inmaculada Álvarez

Location

Los Castillos
Secondary School
(Alcorcón, Spain).
Entrepreneurship
classroom.

Students

25 Students with
ages between 14
and 15.

Materials

Chalkboard
Projector
Computer
Camera

Artistic Component

Graphic design
Photography
Video
Audio-visual editing

Goal

Promote dialogue and collaboration of students towards a concrete and directed goal, observing and appreciating the human rights that are present and absent around them and designing a better future through audio-visual and design tools.

Procedure

Design your ideal world consists of several sessions and is based on project-based learning, so several sessions were designed for its implementation. In the first session, the general objectives of the EducArts! project were explained, as well as the different perspectives and bases. A brainstorming/collaborative debate was also held in which students' conceptions of human rights were explored. In the same session, cooperative groups were organized in which they would work in the different sessions. The project and the organization of the "Design an ideal world" sessions were explained to them: the first part of each session consisted of a presentation of the work done at home and group reflection on it, while the second part focused on explaining the work to be done in the following session.

The sessions and the work carried out were organized in the following weeks:

Week 1: Initial explanation of the project. Structuring and recording of interviews with people close to the pupils, with the subsequent selection of significant fragments and their editing for the production of a video per group with the premise "What would your ideal world be like? The aim was to explain to the students that the results may vary a lot, as they should include people from different sexes, ethnicities, ages, social classes or sexual orientations.

Week 2: Viewing of the interviews and group reflection. Repetition of the previous session, this time with interviews with each member of the group, in order to draw conclusions from them and link them to the content taught on human rights, including personal opinions on the activity itself and the difficulties or opportunities arising from it.

Week 3: Drawing final conclusions from the interviews. Collaborative group workshop in which voting is used to determine the name and slogan of the "ideal world" designed through the interviews. Collaborative design of logos of the ideal world representing the values established as idyllic through the use of web applications and design programmes

Week 4: General presentation and voting of the final project logo. Debate and reflection on advertising and political propaganda in the framework of human rights. Design of a propaganda poster with the project's logo and slogan.

Learning Outcomes

Girl, between 11 and 13 years old: “No racism, equality, no war, no waiting in hospitals, where everyone helps each other and has a good salary. We all have to do our part so that the environment is less polluted”.

Results of three more interviews can be found on Annex 4

What is around us

Concha Maza, Elena Martín, Antonio Serrano, Inmaculada Álvarez

Location

Los Castillos
Secondary School
(Alcorcón, Spain).
Entrepreneurship
classroom.

Students

25 Students with
ages between 14
and 15.

Materials

Chalkboard
Projector
Computer
Camera

Artistic Component

Photography
Oratory

Goal

Explore our immediate surroundings from a pro-human rights approach, seeing those that are fulfilled and violated around us and making proposals for the improvement of spaces.

Procedure

What is around us is a dynamic in which students, in groups, had to make a presentation in which they had to show with their own photographs the human rights that are present and absent around them. The session was divided in two different sessions: While the first one was purely explanatory, about EducArts! and the activity "What is around us", the second one consisted on a showroom of the results.

For the workshop, the students were organized in pairs and asked to do the following:

1. Find a situation that caught their attention for some reason related to Human Rights.
2. Take a photo of that situation that from their point of view supports or promotes human rights.
3. Take a photo of the same situation, but now from a point of view that does not support or promote human rights.
4. Record a video explaining the situation you wanted to represent with the photographs to understand the context as a whole.

In the second session, the photographs were exhibited to the whole group. During the session, the creators explained what they tried to express with them, reflecting on human rights and their importance around them. Most of the students lived in the same area, which led to interesting discussions on how the environment around the school could be improved, either through individual or institutional actions. At the end of the presentations, a final group discussion took place, in which the different conclusions reached by each group after the project and about the project were presented.

Learning Outcomes

Share to understand

Concha Maza, Mara Blanco, Angélica Soleiman, Ana Belén Santos

<p>Location TAI University - School of Art</p>	<p>Students 9 Students with ages between 17 and 23.</p>	<p>Materials Scenario Actors Camera</p>	<p>Artistic Component Theatre Artistic Representation Photography Storytelling</p>
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Goal

To make visible the micro-violations of human rights that occur around us in order to identify them and correct behaviors in order to encourage empathy in the immediate environment, which leads to improvements in groups and in society as a whole.

Procedure

Once the methodology was explained, the young participants were divided between "actors" and "photographers". Actors were asked to tell a "mute" story around the concept of empathy. The actors could not share their story at first, they only staged it for the photographers to take photos according to what they understood of the acting of the actors. Once finished, the actors shared the real story, making sure everything was clear. In a second part, the actors shared with the photographers what the story was about, so the shooting was done keeping the actors' intentions in mind.

The story was shot a third time, this time the photographers "directed" the story by asking the actors to move or stop or stop when they needed to so that the story was told correctly through the images.

After the shooting, educators and students sat down to share impressions. Both stories had a clear purpose: to show everyday moments where empathy plays an important role. The photographers told how they lived and interpreted the stories before and after the actors shared their points of view. The conclusion that was obtained is how an image can change the perspective of reality, what power the artist has to change the meaning of an event according to the perspective from which it is filmed and told.

Learning Outcomes

Narrating ideas

Raphaela Weiss, Hermann Niklas

Location

LIK Akademie of Photo and Design, Linz (Austria).

Students

20 Students with ages between 15 and 20.

Materials

Chalkboard
Projector
Computer
Cardboards

Artistic Component

Artistic writing
Narrative creation

Goal

Promote the search for human rights resources to enhance creative creation inspired by human rights, releasing potentials mainly through literary creation.

Procedure

After talking about EducArts! Methodology, the participants were divided into two different groups that worked separately.

The first group needed some research about human rights and democracy, so an explanatory session was conducted with the help and guidance of the educators. The session took place several days before the Austrian presidential elections, so some questions regarding this topic popped up during the workshop and the debate was active and participatory for all the students involved on the project. Participants were asked to do an online research of photos, biographies and songs related to human rights, but some of the participants had difficulties in writing and reading. The problems in writing and in reading forced us to collect feedback and personal statements referring to human rights as audio-messages instead of written texts or filled out questionnaires. In the second part of the workshop, students had to do the "Linking Poems" activity.

They had to decide one specific topic to work on. Then, they choose parts that later they would have to fit into one sentence. These are called moderation cards. Talking about human rights, some moderation cards could be "minority", "powerful", "dictatorship", "art", "freedom"... There were moderation cards established by the educators and blank ones that should be filled by the students. After all the preparation, all the participants had to write a poem with the words chosen. The workshop ended when all the participants had written down their poems and they had all exposed them to their classmates, which led to a group debate to discuss the conclusions of the session.

With the second group the session was smooth and the created tools and art approaches were used as planned. The group especially liked the creative approach. They had to participate in the activity "Departing to a new land": Students were divided into heterogeneous groups to encourage participation and debate. Immediately after that, they were forced to choose five human rights that they should carry on their backpacks to a recently discovered land, so that they had the future society on their hands. They should decide wisely.

Learning Outcomes

Objects around us

Concha Maza, Víctor Oñoro, María Vallina, Juliane Meirelles

Location
Faculty of Fine Arts, Complutense University, Madrid.

Students
25 Students with ages between 14 and 15.

Materials
Chalkboard
Projector
Computer
Objects

Artistic Component
Sculpture
Photography
Performance
Painting

Goal

Elaborate stories related to human rights to explore the everyday through objects, denouncing injustices and promoting universal rights.

Procedure

The learning scenario was carried out in two different sessions. In the first one, the methodology of the project was explained through a presentation in the classroom. Video visualizations and brainstorming activities were also carried out in relation to universal human rights. Subsequently, examples of artists and works in which objects or actions are decontextualized to reflect injustices were presented. This was followed by an activity with the students in which they were able to express their stories and ideas through simple, everyday objects: plastic bags. In this decontextualization, fashion and design, chaining, sports, violence, love and feelings emerged... The activity to be carried out at home during the week was presented, which consisted in the repetition of the activity with their own objects and objectives arising from individual reflection and the establishment of personal artistic goals.

In the second session, a quick overview of the first session was carried out in order to get into the context of the activity, and the work of the different teams was quickly presented. One by one, they showed their artistic results, among which there were paintings, performances, photographs, sculptures, videos, poems... Many of the students chose modern issues related to the geopolitical situation in certain countries, while others tried to value everyday life. The main themes were war and armed conflicts, sexism and gender oppression, police violence, the right to housing, friendship, family, identity and dignity. After each exhibition, the classmates tried to provide comments and feedback on the projects. After that, a collaborative group discussion was held in which participants reflected on the importance of the activity, the process of developing the artwork and the final results.

Learning Outcomes

Results and Feedback

Results and Feedback

At the end of each activity, both educators and students were asked to fill in a questionnaire regarding general topics related to the development of the session. The average points for each question are shown below, showing the average responses on likert scale (1-5):

QUESTIONS	Los Castillos	Austria	Faro1	Faro2	UCM	TAI	TOTAL
What has been your experience here?							
It has been funny	4,00	4,67	4,26	4,29	4	4,89	4,35
It has been motivating	2,88	4,67	4,26	4,41	4,14	4,67	4,17
It has been enlightening	2,94	4,89	4,42	4,29	4,42	4,67	4,27
It has been fruitful	3,88	4,89	4,47	4,29	4,28	4,89	4,45
This activity has helped me to...							
Be aware of human values	3,65	4,44	4,63	4,47	4,71	4,44	4,39
Understand the role of art and culture in Society	3,47	4,22	4,42	4,53	4	4,75	4,23
Put myself in the other person's place	3,94	4,67	4,47	4,59	4,71	4,44	4,47
Express my point of view with tolerance	3,94	4,63	4,32	4,59	4,42	4,56	4,41
Cooperate with others for the common good	3,82	4,78	4,37	4,47	4,28	4,89	4,43
Through this activity I have worked on...							
Audiovisual techniques	3,82	3,88	3,74	3,71	3,42	3,89	3,74
Digital skills	3,18	4,50	3,68	4,18	2,71	2,78	3,50
Storytelling and narratives	3,59	4,89	3,63	3,88	3	4,44	3,91
Creativity	3,82	5,00	3,89	4,35	4,85	4,67	4,43
Ethics and abstract thinking	3,53	4,67	4,32	4,24	4,71	4,88	4,39
Regarding this specific experience...							
Contents were presented in an orderly manner	4,00	5,00	4,58	4,35	4,71	4,89	4,59
The work environment and duration has been satisfactory	3,94	5,00	4,68	4,53	4,57	5,00	4,62

Complementary to the first table, there's another one table regarding the educator's responses:

QUESTIONS	IES Los Castillos	TAI	Austria	Faro1	Faro2	UCM	TOTAL
Evaluate the following aspects...							
Previous information offered	5,00	5,00	5,00	4,67	4,67	4,75	4,85
Clarity of learning objectives	4,75	5,00	4,88	4,50	4,50	4,75	4,73
Adaptation to learning needs	4,75	5,00	4,88	5,00	5,00	5	4,94
Professional expectations	4,25	4,75	4,50	4,83	4,83	4,75	4,65
I consider this action train on ...							
Audiovisual/digital skills	5,00	5,00	5,00	4,67	4,67	4,5	4,81
Narrative skills	5,00	4,00	4,50	5,00	5,00	4,75	4,71
Creative skills	4,00	4,75	4,38	5,00	5,00	5	4,69
Learning competencies	4,00	4,25	4,13	4,83	4,83	4,5	4,42
I consider these learning activities ...							
Demonstrate and simulate experiences	5,00	4,75	4,88	4,33	4,33	5	4,72
Motivate learning among people	4,75	4,75	4,75	5,00	5,00	5	4,88
Facilitate group work among the participants	4,25	4,50	4,38	4,50	4,50	5	4,52
Facilitate self-learning	4,00	4,00	4,00	4,83	4,83	5	4,44
Help to clarify abstract concepts	4,50	4,25	4,38	4,83	4,83	5	4,63
Create or modify new attitudes of participants	4,75	5,00	4,88	4,50	4,50	5	4,77
Regarding this specific experience ...							
Contents were presented in an orderly manner	5,00	4,75	4,88	4,83	4,83	4,75	4,84
The work environment and duration has been satisfactory	5,00	5,00	5,00	4,83	4,83	5	4,94

Conclusions

Conclusions

Teaching human rights is a duty to future generations, but currently there are no interesting and innovative proposals for transmitting this knowledge to students, so this content is taught in an ineffective and traditional way. In the same way, art, culture and creativity are undervalued tools in educational institutions at any level, which provides an opportunity for educators to exploit their methodological properties. Both elements are necessary to contribute to the comprehensive development of students, and coincidentally, educational strategies that combine them seem to have interesting results.

The methodology presented, together with the pilot activities and the learning outcomes of each one of them show that further research in the framework of human rights and art and creativity is a necessity and that programmes such as EducArts! make sense.

Therefore, we encourage any teacher or educator, after understanding the fundamental visions of the project, to choose ArtScenarios to create learning situations adapted to the context in which he/she finds him/herself. In this way, they can exploit the artistic and creative sphere in adolescents through different practices such as photography, sculpture, video, painting or music and, at the same time, work on human rights, contributing to their support and denouncing injustices. These educational practices should be democratic by themselves, achieving coherence between what is taught and how it is taught, ensuring equal participation, inclusion and non-discrimination, among others.

About us

About us

EducArts! Is an international European project composed by Spanish, Viennese and Portuguese associations and professionals whose main goal is to provide innovative educational experiences related to democracy and human rights, or encourage learners to use art and creativity as tools for participation. With active and collaborative methodologies, their aim is to promote the European values like democracy, respect, equality, inclusion and sustainability, while being heavily consistent on what they teach and how they do it.

The consortium arises from the purpose of combining organizations whose experience is complementary to give more strength to the project's mission. La Cultora was aware of the experience of Contextos in relation to innovative and non-formal educational methodologies with special emphasis on youth, employability skills, diversity, including this organization has been a complement and a learning experience for La Cultora, an organization based in the cultural and creative industries and with a public profile more focused on the sector and its professionals. In addition to this second organization, the incorporation of Sapere Aude arises from the strategy of adding a partner with a strong social profile, since its experience focuses on educating in values, promoting democracy, human rights and European values, and tackling misinformation among young people and racist and xenophobic behavior.

The three visions are complementary and are the great value of EducArts! La Cultora brings the tools of art, culture and creativity to the service of non-formal education and social awareness. The project began in collaboration with UNED, the Spanish distance learning University, and later expanded to the European Union. Since the summer of 2022, the three organizations have maintained contact and collaboration through various meetings, organizing the work thanks to online tools. EducArts! Labs experiences started in September 2022. These were collaborative, creative and democratic environments in which co-responsibility, solidarity and freedom are fundamental pillars, physical spaces that amalgamate the concepts of Citizen Laboratory and Open Classroom. In these labs, they have conducted several educational experiences and actions that aim at bringing knowledge of human rights closer to the population.

Based in Madrid, Spain, and founded in 2014. Coordinator and dynamiser of EducArts! Project. Promotes innovative actions and projects within the Cultural and Creative Industries, creating new forms of work and skills and including a perspective of positive social impact. It has been developing formal education actions (postgraduate studies and university courses) and non-formal education (workshops, promotion of audiovisual or plastic arts oriented to learning in other areas such as social sciences). It was selected, for a Scale Up program, in 2016 by "Madrid Emprande", (Entrepreneurship Area of the Madrid City Council) and the IESE business school. It is currently developing a project based on "Good Practices in Art and Culture for Human Rights", which documents cultural and artistic initiatives related to the promotion of human rights and the objectives of sustainable development (Agenda 2030), in collaboration with the Master in Human Rights and Public Policies from the UNED

Based in Vienna, Austria, and founded in 2009 to promote independent and professional political education through the implementation of projects involving children, youth and adults. Their goal is to encourage the population to develop an interest in politics and democracy, encouraging critical and constructive thinking and working with current issues following a didactic approach and trying to involve the most socially disadvantaged groups, since their participation in society and politics is the clue to build up true democracy. They deal with sensitive and emotional topics such as extremism, respect for human rights in a rapidly changing world, or current political events and crises using a positive and constructive approach. Believing in lifelong learning, they have created and conducted several experiences with children, youth and adults, seeking new methods to strengthen democracy and empower its citizens using artistic and creative writing to implement participatory projects.

Based in Faro, Portugal, and founded in 2016 with the idea of responding to social demands in a comprehensive way and proposing tailored solutions. Its objective is to encourage and promote the empowerment and development of the community as a cornerstone of the processes of change in society through the use of participatory tools to develop competencies and capacities within individuals and organizations. It focuses on culture, media, education, participatory democracy, active citizenship, human rights, intercultural dialogue, non-formal learning, social entrepreneurship and social inclusion through the use of a diverse set of approaches and learning methods in which participants are challenged to use of a critical and reflective thinking to reflex about their own experience. Contextos has extensive experience participating in European projects and cooperates with local and regional public institutions, schools, universities, educational organizations and NGOs.

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Annexes

Declaration of human rights

PREAMBLE

Whereas recognition of the inherent dignity and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world,

Whereas disregard and contempt for human rights have resulted in barbarous acts which have outraged the conscience of mankind, and the advent of a world in which human beings shall enjoy freedom of speech and belief and freedom from fear and want has been proclaimed as the highest aspiration of the common people,

Whereas it is essential, if man is not to be compelled to have recourse, as a last resort, to rebellion against tyranny and oppression, that human rights should be protected by the rule of law,

Whereas it is essential to promote the development of friendly relations between nations,

Whereas the peoples of the United Nations have in the Charter reaffirmed their faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person and in the equal rights of men and women and have determined to promote social progress and better standards of life in larger freedom,

Whereas Member States have pledged themselves to achieve, in cooperation with the United Nations, the promotion of universal respect for and observance of human rights and fundamental freedoms,

Whereas a common understanding of these rights and freedoms is of the greatest importance for the full realization of this pledge,

Now, therefore,

The General Assembly,

Proclaims this Universal Declaration of Human Rights as a common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations, to the end that every individual and every organ of society, keeping this Declaration constantly in mind, shall strive by teaching and education to promote respect for these rights and freedoms and by progressive measures, national and international, to secure their

universal and effective recognition and observance, both among the peoples of Member States themselves and among the peoples of territories under their jurisdiction.

Article 1.

All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.

Article 2.

Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.

Article 3.

Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person.

Article 4.

No one shall be held in slavery or servitude; slavery and the slave trade shall be prohibited in all their forms.

Article 5.

No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

Article 6.

Everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law.

Article 7.

All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination.

Article 8.

Everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for acts violating the fundamental rights granted him by the constitution

constitution or by law.

Article 9.

No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile.

Article 10.

Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.

Article 11.

1. Everyone charged with a penal offence has the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defence.

2. No one shall be held guilty of any penal offence on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a penal offence, under national or international law, at the time when it was committed. Nor shall a heavier penalty be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time the penal offence was committed.

Article 12.

No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks.

Article 13.

1. Everyone has the right to freedom of movement and residence within the borders of each State.

2. Everyone has the right to leave any country, including his own, and to return to his country.

Article 14.

1. Everyone has the right to seek and to enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution.

This right may not be invoked in the case of prosecutions genuinely arising from non-political crimes or from acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 15.

1. Everyone has the right to a nationality.

2. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his nationality nor denied the right to change his nationality.

Article 16.

1. Men and women of full age, without any limitation due to race, nationality or religion, have the right to

marry and to found a family. They are entitled to equal rights as to marriage, during marriage and at its dissolution.

2. Marriage shall be entered into only with the free and full consent of the intending spouses.

3. The family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection by society and the State.

Article 17.

1. Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others.

2. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his property.

Article 18.

Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; this right includes freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief in teaching, practice, worship and observance.

Article 19.

Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers.

Article 20.

1. Everyone has the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association.

2. No one may be compelled to belong to an association.

Article 21.

1. Everyone has the right to take part in the government of his country, directly or through freely chosen representatives.

2. Everyone has the right to equal access to public service in his country.

3. The will of the people shall be the basis of the authority of government; this will shall be expressed in periodic and genuine elections which shall be by universal and equal suffrage and shall be held by secret vote or by equivalent free voting procedures.

Article 22.

Everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security and is entitled to realization, through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality.

Article 23.

1. Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment.

2. Everyone, without any discrimination, has the right to equal pay for equal work.

3. Everyone who works has the right to just and favourable remuneration ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity, and supplemented, if necessary, by other means of social protection.

4. Everyone has the right to form and to join trade unions for the protection of his interests.

Article 24.

Everyone has the right to rest and leisure, including reasonable limitation of working hours and periodic holidays with pay.

Article 25.

Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control.

2. Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection.

Article 26.

1. Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit.

2. Education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace.

3. Parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children.

Article 27.

1. Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits.

2. Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author.

Article 28.

Everyone is entitled to a social and international order in which the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration can be fully realized.

Article 29.

1. Everyone has duties to the community in which alone the free and full development of his personality is possible.

2. In the exercise of his rights and freedoms, everyone shall be subject only to such limitations as are determined by law solely for the purpose of securing due recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others and of meeting the just requirements of morality, public order and the general welfare in a democratic society.

3. These rights and freedoms may in no case be exercised contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 30.

Nothing in this Declaration may be interpreted as implying for any State, group or person any right to engage in any activity or to perform any act aimed at the destruction of any of the rights and freedoms set forth herein.

Videos, EducArts! Perspectives

What we don't know cannot be part of us

In this link you will find an explanatory video for each of the 30 articles that make up the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: <https://www.humanrights.com/what-are-human-rights/videos/born-free-and-equal.html>

In this link there is a video of a TED conference in which Benedetta Berti explains what the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nDgIVseTkuE&t=3s> (4:46 min)

An explanatory video of the EU values can be found at the following link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fh4uX_Grxrg (1:00 min)

What we don't use disappears, doesn't exist

In the following video you can see how creativity can be enhanced, stealing ideas like an artist: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9vUtlNklls> (1:38 min)

- Urban Art: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tlQihqSKRzU>
- Min. 2:53 – 3:12 Art and emotion. Min. 4:40 – 5:08 Public space, space for expression. Min. 8:14 – 13:49 Collective example NSN997. Min.16:46 – 17:41 Collective art and value for the community
- Theater <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CHgeXPfZ0mA>
- Performance <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BgSKECZKWNw>
- Museums <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=N3orQVd315l>
- Cultural Heritage https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=clxFgPP_H2I

What grows from within: From people to action

Video made by the NGO IDEO: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=musmgKEPY2o> (1:55 min). On the website of this organization you can find numerous tips and tools to apply Human-Centered Design: <https://www.ideo.org/tools>

Questions used in “Building Co-Learning Scenarios to promote human rights”

1. It is more important to have a roof over your head than to be able to say what you want.
2. People have the duty to work, but not the right.
3. The basic responsibility of any government is to make sure that every citizen has enough food.
4. The right to rest and leisure is a luxury that only rich countries can afford.
5. How we treat our citizens is our problem, not the problem of the international community.
6. Poor countries should concentrate on providing a basic standard of living for their people before worrying about the Civil and Political Rights of their citizens.
7. Extreme economic inequality is a violation of basic rights.
8. Economic, Social and Cultural Rights express an ideal of the future, but the world, at present, is not prepared to guarantee them.
9. If we cannot guarantee rights, then there is no point in their existence.
10. Some rights are more important than others.
11. Some people naturally have more rights than others.
12. People are homeless because they want to be.
13. Rich people are happier than poor people.
14. It is impossible to completely eradicate poverty.
15. We are not born with rights, we earn them.

Results, interviews from Utopias and Dystopias

- Adult, 80 years old: "I would like the world to be fair, with equality between people, without wars or violence, where everyone has their basic needs met. I want a broad education in terms of knowledge, and population segments, without manipulation and with a free mentality. The economy should be egalitarian, among the human strata, with less wealth accumulated by the oligarchies. I would like there to be no dirt or contamination, and the crops to be organic and free of harmful substances. The work should be reasonable in terms of effort and hours, with enough free time for culture, leisure, sports... Which should always be accessible. Health should be the most important thing because it is what money cannot buy, it must be taken care of even before birth, and it should reach the whole world, it should be truly universal".
- Boy, between 4 and 6 years old: "Let there be trees (laughs) and water, that nature is not treated badly, that people live with food and fruits and vitamins... With life and without wars..."
- Man, between 40 and 55 years old: "There should be a universal democratic system, an egalitarian economy without so many differences, with a free education that allows one to join work in a good way, with equal health, free time is less important but it should be enjoyed by the entire population, and the destruction of the planet should be avoided by taking care of nature".

